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Research Article

Development And Validation of RP-HPLC Method For Simultaneous Estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Bisoprolol Fumarate in Synthetic Mixture

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ABSTRACT

Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate belongs to the Anti-diabetic drugs. Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate used as a treatment of type-2 diabetes mellitus. Another drug is Bisoprolol Fumarate belongs to Beta-1 blocker. Bisoprolol fumarate used as a reduction in blood pressure causing negative chronotropic and inotropic effects. Development and validation of simple, Precise and Accurate RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Bisoprolol Fumarate in synthetic mixture. The validation of this method was achieved as per ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines with the optimized experimental conditions. To achieve the proposed method on C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) column as Stationary Phase and run time was 30 min. The Mobile Phase consists of Acetonitrile: Water (75:25). UV detection was carried out at 272nm. Linearity co-relation co-efficient found is Dapagliflozin is 0.998 and Bisoprolol is 0.999. The method was validated by determining its accuracy, linearity and precision. The proposed method is simple, precise, economical and hence can be applied for routine quality control of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol in synthetic mixture.

INTRODUCTION

The chemical name of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate is (2S)-propane-1,2-diol (2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-2-{4-chloro-3-[(4-ethoxyphenyl)methyl]phenyl}-6-(hydroxymethyl)

oxane-3,4,5-triol hydrate and Bisoprolol Fumarate chemical name is (2E)-but-2-enedioic acid; bis(1-[(propan-2-yl) amino]-3-(4-[[2-(propan-2-yloxy)ethoxy] methyl]phenoxy)propan-2-ol). Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate is the salt

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form of Dapagliflozin, which belongs to the Anti-Diabetic drugs. Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate that inhibits sodium-glucose transporter 2. They lower blood sugar by preventing the reabsorption of glucose by the kidney and are used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. It has a molecular formula $C_{24}H_{35}ClO_9$ with molecular weight 502.99 g/mol. Another drug is Bisoprolol Fumarate is the salt form of Fumaric acid, which belong to the Beta-1 blocker. Bisoprolol is a Cardio selective β_1 -adrenergic antagonist. It blocks the β_1 receptors and has a greater affinity for β_1 receptors than β_2 receptors. β_1 receptors are primarily located in the heart. And also present in the juxtaglomerular cells of the kidneys. By inhibiting these receptors,

Bisoprolol reduces the release of renin, reduces cardiac workload by decreasing contractility and reduction in blood pressure causing negative chronotropic and inotropic effects. It has a molecular formula $C_{18}H_{31}NO_4$. The purpose of this study is to develop a simple, precise and accurate RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Bisoprolol Fumarate in synthetic mixture and to validate the developed method with study of different parameters as per ICH guidelines as no reported RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Bisoprolol Fumarate in synthetic mixture.

Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate

Bisoprolol Fumarate

MATERIALS AND METHOD:**MATERIALS****Table 1.0 Materials & Sources**

Sr. No.	Name of APIs	Source
1	Dapagliflozin	Glenmark Pharmaceuticals LTD
2	Bisoprolol	Schwitz Biotech

Instrumentation

- HPLC instrument with UV-visible detector
- Software: LC Solution
- Column - HYPERSIL ODS C18, 250 mm*4.6 mm
- UV-visible Spectrophotometer - SHIMADZU 1800 Software - UV probe, version- 2.42
- Digital Analytical Balance - Mettler Toledo
- Ultra Sonicator -PS 21
- Controlled temperature water bath
- Hot air Oven – Kesar
- FTIR – SHIMADZU
- Melting Point Apparatus – Gallenkamp Model: 889339

Chemicals and Reagents: Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate API, Bisoprolol Fumarate API, Acetonitrile HPLC Grade, Methanol HPLC Grade, Water: Distil water (Milli-Q), HPLC Grade water.

Preparation of Mobile Phase: RP-HPLC method was followed by isocratic elution technique. Mobile phase comprised of Acetonitrile: Water (75:25 v/v/v %) ratio because it elutes both drugs peak efficiently in short time with satisfactory resolution, tailing factor and theoretical plates.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution A: (Dapagliflozin Stock Solution):

Accurately weighed quantity of Dapagliflozin 10 mg was transferred into 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 1000 µg/ml.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution B: (Bisoprolol stock solution):

Accurately weighed quantity of Bisoprolol 10 mg was transferred into 10 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 1000 µg/mL.

Preparation of standard solution:

Further, dilute 1 mL of standard stock solution A and 0.5 mL of standard stock solution B in to 10 mL of volumetric flask and make up the volume upto the mark with diluent and mixed well. (Dapagliflozin: 10 µg/mL and Bisoprolol :5 µg/mL.)

Chromatographic Conditions:

Table 2.0 Chromatographic Conditions

Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (75:25v/v)
Detection	272nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Detector	UV detector
Injection volume	20 µl
Column oven temperature	40°C
Mode:	ISOCRATIC

Identification And Characterization

The identification of taken standard API for experimental work had done for confirmation of its identity, standard quality and purity. The identification had done by taking IR and UV spectra, solubility study and melting point determination.

Solubility Study:

The solubility of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol practically determined separately by taking 100 mg of both the drugs in 100 ml volumetric flasks, adding required quantity of solvent at room temperature and shaken for few minutes. Solubility data for each study was observed and recorded in Table 4.0.

Table 3.0 Solubility Table

Description Terms	Relative Quantities of solvent for 1 Parts of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1 part
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10 parts
Soluble	From 10 to 30 parts
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100 parts
Slightly soluble	From 300 to 1000 parts
Very slightly soluble	From 1000 to 10000 parts
Practically Insoluble	More than 10000 parts

Table 4.0 Solubility Data for Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

Solvent	Dapagliflozin	Bisoprolol
Water	Very Soluble	Very Soluble
Chloroform	Sparingly Soluble	Sparingly soluble

0.1 N HCL	Soluble	Freely soluble
Acetonitrile	Very Slightly Soluble	Soluble
Methanol	Soluble	Soluble
Ethanol	Sparingly Soluble	Soluble

Identification by Melting Point Determination:

Melting point of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol hydrochloride has been determined. The melting points of the compounds were taken by open capillary method.

Table 5.0 Melting Point of Drugs

Sr. No.	APIs	Melting Point	
		Reported	Measured
1	Dapagliflozin	74.5 °C	74-78 °C
2	Bisoprolol	100°C	98-102°C

IR Spectra:

The IR Spectra of Dapagliflozin with its functional group identification, were shown in the following graph. IR Spectra scanning of sample: Dapagliflozin.

Fig 1.0 IR Spectra of Standard Dapagliflozin

Table 6.0 IR Spectra Interpretation for Dapagliflozin

Groups	General Range(cm-1)	Observed Range(cm-1)
--------	---------------------	----------------------

O-H (s)	3400-3200	3352.28
C-O (s)	1100-11050	1834.55
C-H (s)	2690-2850	2932
C-N (s)	1240-2260	1286
C=O (s)	1640-1680	1655
C≡C (b)	700-1100	763

The IR Spectra of Dapagliflozin with its functional group identification, were shown in the following graph. IR Spectra scanning of sample: Bisoprolol.

Fig 2.0 IR Spectra of Standard Bisoprolol

Table 7.0 IR Spectra Interpretation for Bisoprolol

Groups	General Range(cm-1)	Observed Range(cm-1)
C-H (s)	3300-2800	2813
C=O (s)	1670-1750	1770.60
N-H (s)	3500-3300	3369
C=C	1680-1640	1650.55
C-O	1250-1000	1130.33

Method Development

Selection Of Wavelength:

To determine wavelength for measurement, standard spectra of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol were scanned between 200-400 nm against diluents. Absorbance maxima of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol have detected at 270. Chromatogram was taken at 270 nm, both drugs give good peak height and shape. So, 270 nm was selected for Simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol in their formulation.

Fig 3.0 Overlay UV Spectra of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

Selection Of Column:

For RP-HPLC Method, various columns are available but based on literature survey C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm) was selected over the other columns.

Selection of Mobile phase:

Table 8.0 Trial 1: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :1	
Column	Column
Mobile Phase	Mobile Phase
Detection	Detection
Flow rate	Flow rate
Run Time	Run Time
Observations:	Observations:

Fig 4.0 Trial 1: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer(30:90v/v)

Table 9.0 Trial 2: selection of mobile phase

Trial :2	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (50:50v/v)
Detection	270nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected byt broad peak observed

Fig 5.0 Trial 2: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (50:50v/v)

Table 10.0 Trial 3: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :3	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (80:20v/v)

Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected byt broad peak observed

Fig. 6.0 Trial 3: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer(80:20v/v)

Table 11.0 Trial 4: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :4	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)

Mobile Phase	Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer (60:40v/v)
Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected

Fig 7.0 Trial 4: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer(60:40v/v)

Fig 8.0 Trial 5: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer(70:30v/v)

Table 13.0 Trial 6: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :6	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer (80:20v/v)
Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Peaks detected but broad peaks observed

Fig 9.0 Trial 6: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer(80:20v/v)

Trial :7	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Chloroform: Phosphate Buffer (70:30v/v)
Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	One Peak detected but broad peak observe.

Table 14.0 Trial 7: Selection of Mobile Phase

Fig 10.0 Trial 7: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Chloroform: Acetonitrile (70:30 v/v)

Table 15.0 Trial 8: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :8	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Chloroform: Phosphate Buffer (60:40v/v)

Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	Peak detected but broad peaks observed

Fig 11.0 Trial 8: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Chloroform: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)

Trial :9	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Chloroform: Acetonitrile (50:50v/v)
Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	Peak detected and separated but broad peaks observed

Table 16.0 Trial 9: selection of mobile phase

Fig 12.0 Trial 9: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Chloroform: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)

Table 17.0 Trial 10: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :10	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)

Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (30:70v/v)
Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Observations	No peak detected

Fig 13.0 Trial 10: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Water(30:70v/v)

TRIAL :11	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (50:50v/v)
Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Observations	only one peak detected.

Table 18.0 Trial 11: Selection of Mobile Phase

Fig 14.0 Trial 11: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Water(50:50v/v)

Table 19.0 Trial 12: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :12	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (80:20v/v)

Detection	270nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Observations	Peaks detected and separated, but broad peaks observe.

Fig 15.0 Trial 12: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Water (80:20v/v)

TRIAL :13	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (75:25v/v)
Detection	272nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Observations	Good peaks with Adequate solution were observed.

Table 20.0 Trial 13: Selection of Mobile Phase

Fig 16.0 Trial 13: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Water (75:25 v/v)

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

Chromatographic conditions for optimized mobile phase trial (Bisoprolol):

Table 21.0: optimized mobile phase trial of Bisoprolol

Optimized Method	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water(75:25v/v)
Detection	272nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Detector	UV detector
Injection volume	20 μ l
Column oven temperature	40°C
Mode:	ISOCRATIC

Fig 17.0: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std. Bisoprolol: 6.115 min

Table 22.0: optimized mobile phase trial of Dapagliflozin

Optimized Method	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (75:25v/v)

Detection	272nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Detector	UV detector
Injection volume	20 μ l
Column oven temperature	40°C

Fig 18.0: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std.Dapagliflozin:15.115 min.

Table 23.0: optimized mobile phase trial of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

OPTIMISED METHOD	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (75:25v/v)

Detection	272nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Detector	UV detector
Injection volume	20 µl

Fig 19.0: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std.Dapagliflozin:15.115 min, Bisoprolol: 6.115 min

Introduction Of Method Validation Parameter:

Method validation is the process of documenting or proving that an analytical method provides analytical data acceptable for the intended use. The

need to validate a method and the procedure to be followed are matters of professional judgement, although well-prescribed procedures and guidelines are now available that aid in decision making. According to that the various validation

parameters to validate each and every above stated method are:

- Accuracy and Recovery
- Precision (Repeatability and Reproducibility)
- Linearity
- Range
- Robustness/ Ruggedness
- Limit of Detection (LOD)/ Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Accuracy and Recovery:

The capability of a procedure to generate outcomes close to the actual or standard value (Standard value may be reference value given in official compendia). The chosen concentration for precision investigations must encompass the complete concentration range (i.e. one may the lowest concentration, one may the middle and one may be the last of range).

Accuracy is performed by performing recovery studies by spiking in 2 ways:

1. Spiking of sample with standard (in case placebo are not available).
2. Spiking of placebo with standard.

It can be performed at different level like 50, 100 and 150 % of test concentration or 80, 100, 120% of test concentration.

Reproducibility and Precision:

It is defined as the degree of similarity between test findings obtained from many samplings of the same sample. C.V. or relative standard deviation is capable of expressing it is further classified as reproducibility, repeatability, and intermediate precision. Repeatability is the capability of an analytical procedure to produce identical test findings when performed in a similar setting by the

same operator over a brief period of time. It is stated as R.S.D. when a minimum of three concentrations is analysed at least six times each, and R.S.D. is determined. At least 6 repetitions encompassing 100% of the target concentration or 9 repetitions covering the complete linear range must be assessed. (i.e., three replications for every concentration). Reproducibility is the capacity of an analytical procedure to yield same test findings when applied to identical samples under various conditions and by different analysts. Conditions of operation vary, but the variance is still within acceptable parameters. It is a crucial validation parameter if the procedure must be executed under diverse situations.

Range and Linearity:

It is the capability of the method to generate findings that are directly proportional to the concentration of a specific component in the samples. It is shown via certain mathematical modifications.

1. It may be conducted directly on the material being examined or using a suitable standard and dilution using the suggested approach.
2. It can be accomplished by measuring at least five injections in a series of standards. Eighty to one hundred twenty percent of the recommended concentration range is permissible.
3. A mathematical equation must illustrate the reaction of the sample to the concentration.
4. The linear regression approach requires a substantial zero intercept, and if it is not reached, one must demonstrate that there is no significant influence on accuracy.
5. Another method that may be applied is the response factor, which is generated by dividing

the response by its corresponding concentration to obtain the relative response. On a logarithmic scale, a graph showing relative reaction against concentration is presented. Therefore, the resultant horizontal line must be linear over the full range. Negative deviation is often observed at greater doses. On the graph, a horizontal line is drawn parallel to the x axis to represent 95 to 105 percent of the horizontal line. The reaction is linear with respect to concentration up until the intersection of the horizontal line and the 95 percent line.

It is the concentration interval between which quantitative analysis may be done with appropriate precision and linearity. The analytical method's range is stated in the same units (such as PPM or %).

Robustness:

A technique has the ability to be unaffected by tiny, purposeful changes to operating settings, but these changes are still within the method's range. The effects of these adjustments on the method's output are evaluated. By conducting robustness, one may assess if revalidation is necessary or not. Variable technique parameters include flow rate, mobile phase composition, mobile phase pH, and detection wavelength. This modification can be within the permissible range (i.e., 2% to 5% of the original value). The essential method parameter that identifies the susceptibility of the technique to

change must be reported following ICH rules. However, it is not a registration requirement.

Robustness:

A technique has the ability to be unaffected by tiny, purposeful changes to operating settings, but these changes are still within the method's range. The effects of these adjustments on the method's

output are evaluated. By conducting robustness, one may assess if revalidation is necessary or not. Variable technique parameters include flow rate, mobile phase composition, mobile phase pH, and detection wavelength. This modification can be within the permissible range (i.e., 2% to 5% of the original value). The essential method parameter that identifies the susceptibility of the technique to change must be reported following ICH rules. However, it is not a registration requirement.

Limit of Quantification and Limit of Detection:

It refers to the analytical method's capacity to identify analyte in the presence of a matrix with sufficient accuracy and precision. The method may be able to detect the analyte but not quantify it. There may be confusion between technique sensitivity and LOD. Sensitivity can distinguish between minute differences in concentration. It may be described as the slope of the regression line.

Following methods are available other than signal to noise ratio that are as follows:

1. Visual determination: it is possible to determine by personally injecting the lowest known concentration that is detectable but cannot be measured by mathematical manipulations.
2. Standard deviation of response based on standard deviation of blank: it may be determined by examining the number of blank samples and determining the standard deviation of the blank answers. This approach suggests the capability of a method to provide a response other than analyte concentration.
3. Using slope of regression line to estimate standard deviation of response: one may

measure the S.D. of regression line of a given calibration curve or use S.D. of intercept.

4. It is also calculable using the mathematical formulae shown below.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Analytical method Validation

Linearity

For the purpose of linearity, accurately weighed amount of Dapagliflozin (10 mg), and Bisoprolol

(10 mg) was taken into the volumetric flask (10 ml) and volume of the flask was raised to 10 ml with methyl alcohol to give stock solution containing 100 µg/ml of Dapagliflozin, and 100 µg/ml of Bisoprolol. Various aliquots from this stock solution were transferred to another 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was raised to the mark with mobile phase to give final solutions containing 5+2.5, 7.5+3.75, 10+5, 12.5+6.25 µg/ml and 15+7.5 µg/ml of Dapagliflozin and Bisoprolol respectively.

Table 24.0 Linearity data for Dapagliflozin

Linearity level	Conc. (µg/ml)	Dapagliflozin		
		Mean Area	± SD (n=5)	% RSD
50 % Linearity	5	364231	364231± 3341.04	0.92
75% Linearity	7.5	575799	575799± 2516.04	0.44
100% Linearity	10	723754	723754± 521.06	0.07
125% Linearity	12.5	864343	864343± 316.70	0.04
150% Linearity	15	1049879	1049879± 1957.27	0.18

Table 25.0 Linearity Data for Bisoprolol

Linearity level	Conc. (µg/ml)	Bisoprolol		
		Mean Area	± SD (n=5)	% RSD
50 % Linearity	2.5	102791	102791 ± 149.01	0.14
75% Linearity	3.75	164800	164800± 306.25	0.19
100% Linearity	5.00	205650	205650± 1086.79	0.53
125% Linearity	6.25	247038	247038± 1749.10	0.71
150% Linearity	7.5	305352	305352± 1083.92	0.35

Fig 20.0: Overlain Linearity Spectra of Dapagliflozin and Dapagliflozin

Fig 21.0: Calibration curve of Dapagliflozin

Table 26.0 Linearity results for Dapagliflozin and Bisoprolol

Regression Analysis	Dapagliflozin	Bisoprolol
Concentration Range	5-15 µg/mL	2.5-7.5 µg/mL
Regression equation	$y = 68979x + 25475$	$y = 40978x + 1019.7$
Correlation co-efficient	0.998	0.999

Precision

The data for repeatability for Dapagliflozin and Bisoprolol is shown in table 6.13. The % R.S.D For Repeatability data was found to be 1.10 % for LID and 1.45 % for DIL.

Repeatability

Table 27.0 Repeatability data for Dapagliflozin and Bisoprolol

Drugs	Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Peak Area ± SD	%RSD
Dapagliflozin	10	724598 ± 2986.2	0.64
Bisoprolol	5	208045.61 ± 3205.55	0.45

Inter-day precision

0.34 % for Dapagliflozin and 0.06 -0.70 % for Bisoprolol.

The data for inter-day precision for Dapagliflozin and Bisoprolol is shown in table 6.14. The % R.S.D for intraday precision was found to be 0.18-

Inter-Day Precision for Dapagliflozin:

Table 28.0 Inter-day precision data for estimation of Dapagliflozin

Level	µg/mL	Area	Mean	SD	RSD
50%	5	365642	366438	1260.253	0.34392
		367891			
		365781			

100%	10	724536	725929.3	3396.566	0.467892
		723451			
		729801			
150%	15	1087912	1085572	2027.092	0.18673
		1084451			
		1084353			

Inter-Day Precision for Bisoprolol:**Table 29.0 Inter-day precision data for estimation of Bisoprolol**

Level	µg/mL	Area	Mean	SD	RSD
50%	5	365718	364146.3	2524.798	0.693347
		365487			
		361234			
100%	10	723451	724131.3	1174.044	0.162131
		725487			
		723456			
150%	15	1085467	1084756	6174831	0.056924
		1084351			
		1084451			

Intra-Day Precision for Bisoprolol:**Table 31.0 Intra-day precision data for estimation of Bisoprolol**

Level	µg/mL	Area	Mean	SD	RSD
50%	5	365718	364146.3	2524.798	0.693347
		365487			
		361234			
100%	10	723451	724131.3	1174.044	0.162131
		725487			
		723456			
150%	15	1085467	1084756	6174831	0.056924
		1084351			
		1084451			

Accuracy:

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from synthetic mixture at three level standard additions. Percentage recovery for

Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 99.48-99.78% and 99.33-100.59 % respectively. The results are shown in table 32.0 – 33.0.

Recovery For Dapagliflozin:**Table 32.0 Recovery data for Dapagliflozin**

Recovery Level	mg added	Mg recovered	% Recovery	Mean (%)
50%	5.02	5.00	99.60	99.87
	5.02	4.99	99.40	
	5.02	5.05	100.60	
	10.05	9.99	99.40	

100%	10.05	10.06	100.10	99.60
	10.05	9.98	99.30	
150%	15.20	15.45	101.64	101.23
	15.20	15.31	100.72	
	15.20	15.40	101.32	

Recovery For Bisoprolol:

Table 33.0 Recovery data for Bisoprolol

Recovery Level	mg added	Mg recovered	% Recovery	Mean (%)
50%	2.51	2.48	98.80	100.00
	2.51	2.53	100.80	
	2.51	2.52	100.40	
100%	5.10	5.02	98.43	98.43
	5.10	5.03	98.63	
	5.10	5.01	98.24	
150%	7.54	7.51	99.60	99.87
	7.54	7.52	99.73	
	7.54	7.56	100.27	

LOD and LOQ:

The limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) was found to be as per below:

Table 34.0 LOD and LOQ Limit for Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

Dapagliflozin		Bisoprolol	
LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
2.40	3.15	1.30	2.55

Robustness:

The method is found to be robust as the results were not significantly affected by slight variation in Mobile Phase Composition and flow rate of

mobile phase. The results are shown in table 35. Variation seen was within the acceptable range respect to peak asymmetry and theoretical plates, so the method was found to be robust.

Table 35.0 Robustness data for Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

Parameter	Level of Change	Effect on assay volume			
		Dapagliflozin		Bisoprolol	
		Assay \pm SD	RSD	Assay \pm SD	RSD
Flow rate	0.9 mL/min	97.70 \pm 0.50	0.50	98.92 \pm 0.40	0.40
	1.0 mL/min	96.70 \pm 0.50	0.49	96.92 \pm 0.48	0.48
	1.1 mL/min	101.09 \pm 0.72	0.72	96.99 \pm 0.83	0.83
Mobile phase composition	25:75	96.47 \pm 0.53	0.53	100.22 \pm 1.43	1.43
	27:73	96.39 \pm 0.99	0.98	100.04 \pm 1.06	1.06
	23:77	99.51 \pm 0.67	0.67	99.45 \pm 0.77	0.78

Analysis of marketed product:

The proposed method was successfully applied to analysis of the commercially available tablet

formulation. The % drugs were found satisfactory, which is comparable with the corresponding label claim.

Table 36.0 Analysis of Marketed Formulations

Drug	Amount taken (µg/mL)	Amount found (µg/mL)	% Assy
Dapagliflozin	10	9.93±0.04	99.30±1.20
Bisoprolol	5	5.03 ±0.10	100.60±1.07

Summary Of Method Validation:

Summary of validation parameter are shown in below table. All the parameters for substance met the criteria of ICH guideline for the method validation and found to be suitable for routine quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The result of linearity, accuracy, precision

proved to be within limits with lower limits of detection and quantification. Robustness of method was confirmed as no significant in the were observed on analysis by subjecting the method to slight change in the method condition. Assay results obtained by proposed method are fair agreement.

Table 37.0 Summary of validation parameter of RP-HPLC method

Optimized chromatographic Condition	
Stationary Phase	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Water (75:25v/v)
Detection wave Length	270 nm
Flow rate	1 ml/minute
Run time	30 minutes
Retention Time	Dapagliflozin: 15.115 min, Bisoprolol: 6.115 min.

Table 38.0 Validation Parameters

Validation Parameters				
Parameter	Limit	Result		Conclusion
		Dapagliflozin	Bisoprolol	
Linearity and Range	R2> 0.995	0.998 (5-15µg/mL)	0.999 (2.5-7.5µg/mL)	Method was linear
Repeatability	RSD<2	0.64	0.45	Method was repeatable
LOD	-	2.40	1.30	-
LOQ	-	3.15	2.55	-
Intra-day Precision	RSD<2	0.05-0.69	0.19-0.40	Method was precise
Inter-Day Precision	RSD<2	0.18-0.34	0.06-0.70	Method was precise
% Recovery	98-102%	50%-99.87%	50%-100%	Method was accurate
		100%-99.60%	100%-98.43%	
		150%-101.23%	150%-99.87%	
Robustness	RSD<2	0.41– 0.63	0.40-0.91	Method was robust
Assay%		99.30 ±1.20	100.60±1.07	-

CONCLUSION:

A simple, economic, specific, accurate and precise RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and bisoprolol fumarate in synthetic mixture. All method validation parameters lie within its acceptance criteria as per ICH Q2(R1) guideline so we can conclude that methods are specific, linear, accurate and precise. In RP-HPLC method, Linearity was observed in the concentration range of Dapagliflozin 5-15 µg/ml and Bisoprolol 2.5-7.5 µg/ml with correlation coefficient of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol 0.998 & 0.999. The proposed method was successfully applied for the simultaneous estimation of both drugs in combined dosage form. The Assay value of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 99.30% & 100.60%. The Mean recovery was found to be in the range Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol of 99.87 – 101.23% & 99.87 – 100.0%. LOD and LOQ were found to be Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol of 2.40 µg/ml and 3.15 µg/ml & 1.30 µg/ml and 2.55 µg/ml. The % RSD of repeatability precision, intra-day precision & inter-day precision of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 0.64% & 0.45%, 0.18-0.34% & 0.06-0.70%, 0.05-0.69% & 0.19-0.40%. It indicated that the method is precise. The % RSD of Robustness change in Flow rate Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 0.041%-0.63% & 0.40%-0.91%. Hence, proposed method is well suited for simultaneous estimation in synthetic mixture. It can be easily and conveniently adopted for routine analysis of semi solid dosage form.

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